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Benefits of sustainable Public Transportation

People across the globe are increasingly realizing the need to reducing carbon emission. Despite this, very few are taking steps to adopt sustainable transport as a way of curbing carbon emission. Sustainable transportation is any means of transport that impacts least on the social, climatic, economic and environmental debates and the ability to supply the source energy indefinitely. This paper aims to make a contribution to the understanding the benefit that come with the adoption of sustainable public transport means with focus on driverless rail transport.

Contemporary means of transport have significant negative impact on the environment. 20-25% of carbon dioxide emission and energy consumption is associated with these modes of transport since they use fossil fuels that account to 97% of world carbon dioxide emission (Yang 1154). 2.4 million premature deaths occur annually due to outdoor pollution. Black carbon particularly, is known to cause carcinogenic and respiratory complications, and is also a significant player in climate change (Wee 23). The intervention into this will mean mitigation I climate change and public health.

Benefits resulting from using driverless-rail-transport are not only environmental, but are also a social and economical as well. Being a cheaper means of transport in comparison with others, the consumers can avoid spending on the escalating prices of fuel, parking fees and traffic congestions. Other social benefits include access to mobility, supporting economic development,

reducing noise and air pollution and increased public health and safety (Boren 67). Low-carbon transport does have significant and quantifiable co-benefits, based on case studies from Germany, Singapore, India and Colombia.

This mode of transport has health benefits too, due to reduced carbon in the air that would have come from the usage of numerous cars, which have health hazards caused. Road carnages that arise from human error are also a greatly avoided by the adoption of driver-less trains.

People spend a lot in daily traveling energy. A person in Europe, where sustainable transport is widely used, uses four times less energy in transportation. It's estimated that people of New York save up to \$19 billion annually by using rail transport. (Boren 69). By the use of sustainable means of transport as trains, the costs of fuels are saved.

The cost of building electric train rails are estimated to cost a tenth less than building highways. (Yang, 1126). And since a train stands in place of many vehicles, the cost of repairing and maintaining the rail system costs less than a high way used by so many cars in an hour. This tremendously lowers the infrastructure construction cost.

The larger sums of money used in maintenance of roads and highways are saved rail transport is adopted; this money can be saved by Governments and channeled to other more important initiatives for the betterment of the lives of the people. The American transportation department spent \$ 63.2 Billion in maintaining Highways in 2008 alone (Yang 1161). This is a large sum that could have been used in a more progressive way is people used trains.

The adoption of driverless trains greatly helps ease congestion in roads, accidents and traffic jams. This helps reduce injury, death and property damage and congestion relief. When rail transport is employed, these problems are confronted resulting in paving way for economic and social development (Boren 67).

Joblessness is one of the most serious problems that face nations today. To help curb this, as opposed to owning cars, jobs will be created in design, construction, technology, manufacturing and maintenance of these mass modes of transport among other fields. (Yang1154). This will create thousands of employment opportunities. Therefore when transportation problems are being confronted, joblessness is being confronted as well.

There is also increase in speed of travel from an average of 96 KMH to an average 161 KMH for both the passenger and the driver by nearly 33%. Passengers spend about 3 billion hours annually driving in cars. If this time is saved using the electric train, with a time value of \$6 per hour, a total of % 18 billion worth of unproductive time is saved.

However, the mass public transport means has certain social shortfalls. In this type of development, for example in rail transport, the non-driver means of transport has much lower accessibility level and lacks travel choice. This has effect on both the equity and the efficiency of transport distribution and, thus, is socially unfair and inadequate (Boren70).

Conclusion

Population has increased significantly for the last half a century, this means more carbon emission into the environment, among other social and economic effects. This therefore is the primary reason for the adoption of sustainable public transport means such as the use of rail transport. Research and development of renewable and sustainable energy sources should therefore be a primary objective of governments that are faced with problems of congestion among others.

Works Cited

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